

Digital Preservation Basics

“Digital Preservation refers to the series of managed activities necessary to ensure continued access to digital materials for as long as necessary ... [digital preservation] refers to all of the actions required to maintain access to digital materials beyond the limits of media failure or technological and organisational change.” - Digital Preservation Coalition

Outlined below are some key actions associated with digital preservation.

Fixity Checking

Fixity checking is a method that involves verifying that the file has not been altered or changed. This ensures that the integrity of the file is maintained. A common way to conduct fixity checking is to use checksums, a unique alpha-numerical sequence, that identifies the file.

Metadata

Metadata is information that provides context about the digital files. Metadata for digital preservation includes information needed to manage the digital files over time. This information can be contextual, historical or technical in nature.

Refreshing

Refreshing is a method that involves copying digital content from one storage medium to another storage medium of the same type. During this process there is no change to the bitstream of the file. Storage media refresh needs to occur to address storage decay or obsolescence. It is one component of a successful digital preservation program.

Replication

Replication is a method that involves ensuring that multiple copies of the digital files are stored in different geographic locations to mitigate loss in the event of a disaster, (fire, flood, system failures, cyberattack, etc.).

Normalization

Normalization involves converting copies of the original files to a select few non-proprietary and widely available and used formats.

Migration

Migration involves transforming data from one format to a newer version of the same format. It may also involve the migration of a file to a different format to ensure continued access.

Planning & Documentation

Planning and documentation are key components of a digital preservation program. Digital preservation planning can include risk analysis, program benchmarking, and format strategies. Documentation can include digital preservation policies, frameworks, and workflows.

